

SELF-CONTAINED COST-EFFECTIVE PLASTIC RECYCLING FACILITIES

Clinton D. Switzer¹, Siddhesh Chaudhari², Anuj Maheshwari³, Frank D. Blum³, and Ranji Vaidyanathan²

¹Zero Plastic, 816 N Owasso Ave Tulsa OK 74106

Email: clinton.switzer@zeroplasticresearch.com, web page: <http://zeroplasticresearch.com>

²Department of Mechatronics, Materials and Manufacturing Engineering, Oklahoma State University
700 N. Greenwood Avenue, Tulsa, Oklahoma, United States

Email: Siddhesh.chaudhari@okstate.edu

³Department of Chemistry, Oklahoma State University
Stillwater, United States

Email: anuj.maheshwari@okstate.edu

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ABSTRACT

The increasing use of plastics demands effective end-of-life waste management, yet recycling facilities remain inaccessible in many areas, especially remote regions seeking sustainable solutions. The “Zero Plastic” project explores innovative methods to reuse waste plastics with minimal processing. This study focuses on two plastic waste streams: stretch wraps—typically made of LLDPE, LDPE, or HDPE and PET bottles, including labels and caps, evaluating the mechanical properties of recycled molded products. Stretch wrap samples were compression molded at 180 °C under 2 MPa for 10 minutes, yielding a flexural strength of 15 MPa and a modulus of 420 MPa. Recycled PET (rPET) molded at 265 °C under 1 MPa for 4 minutes achieved 76 MPa strength and 2800 MPa modulus. However, labels and caps introduced immiscibility challenges. Using 10-wt% Lotader AX8840 compatibilizer reduced rPET’s flexural strength and modulus to 64 MPa and 2000 MPa, respectively, while increasing elongation to 4.5%, correlating with higher creep compliance due to enhanced flexibility. Despite these improvements, PET bottle waste blended with compatibilizer remained brittle and was unsuitable for further testing. Various parts, including bricks and sheets of thicknesses 6.35 mm to 19 mm and lengths from 40 cm to 86 cm, were successfully molded from stretch wrap, demonstrating a feasible, cost-effective recycling pathway. Preliminary life cycle assessments showed significant environmental benefits: recycling stretch wrap could save 52,300 MJ of embodied energy and prevent 558 metric tons of CO₂ emissions (44% and 13% reductions, respectively). PET bottle recycling offers even higher potential, with 146,000 MJ energy savings and a 4900-metric-ton reduction in CO₂ emissions (53% and 39% reductions). Future work will enhance manufacturing processes and explore plastic blending strategies to establish sustainable, decentralized recycling facilities where such infrastructure is currently lacking.

1 INTRODUCTION

Recent research underscores both the opportunities and limits of mechanical recycling for plastics. Mechanical recycling remains the most energy-efficient and environmentally favorable option, particularly for single-polymer streams like PET, HDPE, or LDPE, and can achieve significant reductions in carbon footprint when properly implemented. However, studies show that even with optimized collection and sorting, mechanical recycling will typically only capture 30 to 40% of plastic waste, constrained by challenges such as polymer degradation, contamination, and the presence of complex multi-material products. As Klotz et al. noted, mechanical processes are limited in addressing

diverse plastic grades and achieving high-quality recycled outputs suitable for demanding applications [1]. This gap highlights why efforts to decentralize recycling via smaller, stand-alone facilities must consider the technical feasibility of handling mixed waste streams without compromising product quality or environmental gains [2].

In addition to mechanical approaches, chemical and solvent-based recycling processes are emerging as potential solutions for plastics unsuitable for melting and reprocessing. Techniques like pyrolysis, gasification, and depolymerization can transform mixed or contaminated plastics into valuable monomers or fuels, theoretically producing outputs comparable to virgin materials. However, these technologies remain costly, energy-intensive, and largely unproven at industrial scale, with uncertainties in life-cycle impacts and process economics. Life cycle assessments emphasize the importance of evaluating recycling technologies not just by greenhouse gas emissions but also by factors like net fossil carbon balance, landfill diversion, and plastic leakage to the environment [3-4]. As such, while small-scale recycling plants offer promise for rural and remote areas, their viability hinges on careful integration of mechanical and chemical pathways, robust sorting infrastructure, and economic models capable of offsetting high capital and operational costs.

Even though mechanical recycling remains the preferred method for plastic waste management, the cost of establishing a conventional Materials Recovery Facility (MRF) is prohibitively high for most communities, particularly in rural or remote regions. To address this challenge, Zero Plastic LLC and Oklahoma State University collaborated under a U.S. Army SBIR Phase I effort (Contract No. W51701-23-C-0246) [5] to explore the feasibility of developing a self-contained, mobile recycling facility housed inside a shipping container. The goal was to create a compact system capable of recycling common plastic waste streams, such as stretch wraps and plastic bottles, into useful products with minimal sorting and processing requirements. Building on this work, the present study investigates the feasibility of producing value-added products from post-consumer plastics using such stand-alone facilities. We focused on characterizing recycled stretch wrap materials and recycled PET blends, both in their raw state and with compatibilization strategies aimed at improving mechanical properties. A range of thermal and mechanical analyses was conducted to evaluate material performance and processing behavior. The following sections describe the materials used, the experimental methods employed, and the results obtained, offering insights into the technical viability and limitations of decentralized recycling systems for mixed plastic waste streams.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

This study utilized post-consumer plastic waste streams, specifically stretch wrap waste composed of linear low-density polyethylene (LLDPE), low-density polyethylene (LDPE), and high-density polyethylene (HDPE), as well as recycled polyethylene terephthalate (rPET) flakes obtained from commercial reclaimers. Recycled polypropylene (rPP) was also incorporated for blending studies with rPET. To enhance interfacial compatibility between immiscible polymers, Lotader AX8840 (Arkema Inc.), an ethylene-acrylic ester-glycidyl methacrylate terpolymer, was employed as a compatibilizer at concentrations of 5-wt% and 10-wt%.

2.2 Sample Preparation

Post-consumer plastics were initially cut or shredded into small flakes using a Vecoplan VAZ 800 shredder. Blends involving rPET and rPP, with or without compatibilizer, were compounded using a Brabender Plasti-Corder torque rheometer at 235°C for 5 minutes at a rotor speed of 60 rpm to achieve homogeneous dispersion. Compression molding was performed on a Carver hydraulic press under different conditions depending on the polymer type: stretch wrap samples were molded at 180°C under 2 MPa for 10 min., while rPET-based samples were molded at 265°C under 1 MPa for 4 min. The resulting products included sheets and bricks, with thicknesses ranging from 6.35 mm to 19 mm, and lengths and widths between 40 cm and 86 cm.

2.3 Thermal and Mechanical Characterization

Thermal and mechanical characterization of the recycled plastics was performed to evaluate their suitability for manufacturing applications. Thermal transitions were analyzed using a TA Instruments Q2000 Differential Scanning Calorimeter (DSC), with samples of 5–10 mg subjected to a heat-cool-heat cycle from 30 °C to 300 °C at a rate of 3 °C/min under a nitrogen atmosphere. The key parameters measured included glass transition temperatures (T_g), melting points (T_m), and crystallization behaviors. Mechanical properties were assessed through flexural testing conducted using an Instron Universal Testing Machine following ASTM D790 standards, employing a span length of 50 mm and a crosshead speed of 2 mm/min to determine flexural strength, modulus, and elongation at break. Additionally, dynamic mechanical properties were examined using a TA Instruments Q800 DMA in dual cantilever mode across a temperature range of 30 °C to 80 °C, capturing data on storage modulus, loss modulus, creep compliance, and time-temperature superposition behavior.

The analytical techniques were crucial for understanding the inherent challenges of recycling mixed plastic waste streams, such as polyolefin films and PET bottles, which differ significantly in chemical structure, melting behavior, and mechanical performance. In this study, recycled plastic streams—including stretch wraps composed of polyethylene blends and rPET materials—were systematically analyzed to evaluate their thermal behavior and mechanical integrity, both in their unmodified states and after the addition of compatibilizers. The results from DSC and DMA provided critical insights into the compatibility of blended polymers and the effectiveness of processing methods used, informing the design and feasibility of stand-alone, containerized recycling facilities capable of converting heterogeneous plastic waste into functional products.

2.4 Life Cycle Assessment

A preliminary life cycle assessment (LCA) was performed to quantify the environmental impacts of the recycling operations, focusing on embodied energy and greenhouse gas emissions, using the LCA calculator provided by the REMADE Institute, of which Oklahoma State University was a member during the SBIR project [6]. Calculations integrated process-specific energy data and emissions factors drawn from literature and operational data obtained during the SBIR Phase I project. These assessments provided insights into the potential sustainability benefits of implementing localized, stand-alone recycling facilities.

2.5 Fabrication of Molded Products and Equipment Used

Post-consumer plastics, including stretch wrap and rPET bottles, were first shredded into flakes using a Vecoplan VAZ 800 industrial shredder, producing fragments approximately 10–20 mm in size to facilitate further processing. For blends requiring improved homogeneity, the shredded material was fed into a Filabot EX6 single-screw extruder, operated at barrel temperatures between 170°C and 220°C and screw speeds ranging from 10 to 40 rpm. In certain trials, extruded strands were cooled and pelletized using a Filabot Pelletizer, yielding uniform feedstock suitable for consistent molding operations. This sequence ensured adequate mixing, particularly in blends containing compatibilizers such as Lotader AX8840. The key equipment used in these processes—including the shredder, extruder, pelletizer, and compression molding press is shown in Figure 1.

Final products, including sheets, bricks, tiles, and other molded components, were fabricated using a Carver hydraulic compression molding press. Process parameters varied depending on the polymer type: stretch wrap blends were molded at 180°C under 2 MPa for 10 min, while rPET and rPET blends were molded at 265 °C under 1 MPa for 4 min. Custom-designed steel molds were utilized to shape parts into dimensions ranging in thickness from 6.35 mm to 19 mm, with lengths and widths between 40 cm and 86 cm. These molded parts were subsequently evaluated for mechanical performance and surface quality to assess the feasibility of producing durable products from localized, stand-alone recycling operations.

Figure 1. Key equipment used for stand-alone recycling, including the shredder, extruder, pelletizer, and compression molding press.

To further illustrate the stand-alone recycling system developed in this study, Figure 2 presents a schematic layout of the self-contained manufacturing facility housed inside a standard shipping container. This diagram shows the workflow and spatial arrangement of the main processing equipment, including the shredder, extruder, pelletizer, and compression molding press, all integrated into a compact footprint designed for deployment in remote or rural settings. The layout enables localized recycling operations, minimizing the need for transportation to centralized facilities.

Figure 2. Schematic of the shipping container with the various equipment.

Figure 3 shows photographs of some of the primary equipment used in the recycling process. The Brabender Prep Center (Figure 3a) served as the primary compounding system for blending recycled polymers and compatibilizers under controlled temperature and shear conditions. It enabled thorough mixing of rPET, rPP, and Lotader AX8840, producing homogenous blends for subsequent molding operations. The Vecoplan VAZ 800 industrial shredder (Figure 3b) was employed for the initial size reduction of post-consumer plastics, producing flakes (Figure 3c) approximately 10–20 mm in size to facilitate downstream processing.

Figure 3. (a) Brabender prep center (b) Industrial shredder (c) shredded pieces.

Custom-designed steel molds, illustrated in Figure 4, were fabricated to produce a variety of product geometries, including beams, bricks, and flat sheets, tiles. The molds varied in size to accommodate different applications, with part thicknesses ranging from 6.35 mm to 19 mm and lengths and widths between 40 cm and 86 cm. These molds were engineered to endure high processing temperatures and pressures, ensuring proper consolidation and dimensional accuracy in the recycled polymer products.

Figure 4. Molds for beams, bricks and sheets.

Finally, Figure 5 displays examples of finished products manufactured during the project. These images showcase the successful conversion of recycled stretch wrap and rPET blends into functional items such as panels, tiles, and construction bricks. The molded products provide visual evidence of the system's capacity to create usable, value-added components from heterogeneous plastic waste streams, reinforcing the technical feasibility of decentralized recycling solutions.

Figure 5. Examples of recycled parts fabricated on the equipment shown in Figure 1 – stackable blocks made from HDPE and stretch wrap (150 mm x 100 mm), beams made from stretch wrap (250 mm x 100 mm), and 900 mm x 900 mm x 6.5 mm thick sheets.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The following sections present the thermal and mechanical characterization of recycled plastic materials processed using the stand-alone, containerized recycling system. Results are discussed in the

context of polymer compatibility, processing behavior, and the feasibility of producing durable, value-added products from post-consumer plastic waste streams. Where relevant, findings are compared with literature data and insights gained during the project to highlight both the potential and limitations of localized recycling solutions.

3.1 DSC Analysis of Stretch Wrap

DSC thermograms for post-consumer stretch wrap samples (Figure 6) revealed the thermal complexity of mixed polyethylene waste streams. Two distinct melting endotherms were observed: one around 109–114 °C, attributed to low-density polyethylene (LDPE) components, and another near 122 °C, corresponding to high-density polyethylene (HDPE) fractions. The presence of multiple melting peaks reflects the varied composition of the stretch wrap waste, which includes LDPE, LLDPE, and potentially blends with other polyolefins. Additionally, the broadness and reduced intensity of these peaks, compared to neat HDPE or LDPE, suggest lower crystallinity and possible molecular weight degradation resulting from prior processing and recycling steps, a typical phenomenon in recycled polyolefin materials.

Figure 6. DSC thermograms for stretch wrap and polyethylene blends.

3.2 DSC Thermograms of rPP and rPET

DSC thermograms for recycled PET (rPET) and recycled polypropylene (rPP) are shown in Figures 7 and 8, with corresponding thermal transitions summarized in Table 1. The thermogram for rPET (Figure 7) exhibits a crystallization exotherm at approximately 187 °C and a prominent melting endotherm at 248 °C, consistent with the thermal behavior of semi-crystalline PET materials. These results confirm that the recycled PET retains significant crystalline character, suggesting it may still be suitable for remanufacturing applications requiring thermal stability.

The thermogram for rPP (Figure 8) displays multiple thermal transitions. A primary melting peak is observed at approximately 162 °C, which corresponds to isotactic polypropylene. Additionally, smaller melting and crystallization features at approximately 126 °C and 116 °C, respectively, indicate the presence of polyethylene (PE) contamination within the rPP stream. This overlapping of thermal transitions suggests partial immiscibility and heterogeneity in the recycled rPP material. Such PE contamination is common in post-consumer recycled streams and can influence both mechanical properties and processability.

These thermal analyses indicate that while both rPET and rPP exhibit recognizable melting and crystallization behavior, the presence of impurities and mixed phases, particularly in rPP, could complicate subsequent processing or blending operations. This underscores the importance of careful material characterization when designing stand-alone recycling systems to produce consistent, high-quality recycled products.

Figure 7. DSC thermogram for rPET.

Figure 8: DSC thermogram for rPP.

Sample	Melting temperature, °C (T_m)	Crystallization temperature, °C (T_c)
rPET	248	187
rPP with PE (as a contamination)	162	127
	126	116

Table 1. Observed thermal transitions for rPET and rPP.

3.3 DMA Results for rPET Blends

Dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) was conducted to evaluate the viscoelastic behavior of recycled stretch wrap materials. The time-temperature superposition (TTS) creep compliance curve for stretch wrap, shown in Figure 9, displays a steadily increasing trend over time. This behavior reflects the inherently lower stiffness and higher ductility typical of polyolefin-based films, indicating that under sustained stress, these materials exhibit significant time-dependent deformation. This is consistent with flexural test results, which showed lower modulus values for stretch wrap compared to recycled PET. For recycled PET (rPET) samples, substantial differences in viscoelastic behavior were observed depending on compatibilizer content, as shown in Figure 10.

Figure 9. Time-temperature superposition (TTS) curve for stretch wrap.

Figure 10. Time-temperature superposition (TTS) curve for rPET with and without compatibilizer (showing sample #s).

Pure rPET exhibited the lowest creep compliance, reflecting its stiff and brittle nature with minimal deformation under sustained loading. In contrast, blending rPET with Lotader AX8840 compatibilizer led to progressively higher creep compliance values. The rPET/compat 95/5 blend showed increased compliance relative to pure rPET, while the 90/10 blend exhibited the highest compliance among the samples tested. These results indicate that the addition of compatibilizer softens the polymer matrix,

enhancing ductility and flexibility but simultaneously reducing stiffness. This behavior aligns with the flexural test results, where compatibilized blends displayed increased elongation at break and lower modulus compared to pure rPET. The DMA data thus confirm that compatibilization effectively modifies the viscoelastic properties of recycled PET, improving toughness and processability at the expense of rigidity.

3.4 Compatibilization

The recycling of mixed plastic waste streams poses significant challenges due to the inherent immiscibility between different polymer types, which leads to poor interfacial adhesion and compromised mechanical properties. Studies such as those by Maris et al. [7] and Imamura et al. [8] emphasize that while compatibilization offers a promising pathway to blend polymers like PET, PP, and PE, it frequently comes with trade-offs. Compatibilizers can reduce interfacial tension and promote morphological stability, but they also often lead to decreased tensile strength and modulus, driven by disruption of crystalline domains or the introduction of softer segments into the polymer matrix. Friedrich et al. [9] further demonstrate that purely chemical approaches might be insufficient and that morphological strategies—such as creating microfibrillar structures can significantly enhance the mechanical performance of polymer blends, particularly in PET/PP systems.

Our current study mirrors many of these literature findings. The addition of Lotader AX8840 compatibilizer to rPET/rPP blends indeed led to an increase in elongation at break from 2.5% to 4.3%, signalling improved ductility and toughness. However, consistent with observations by Imamura et al. [8], we also recorded a significant reduction in flexural strength and modulus dropping from 76.8 MPa and 2810 MPa in pure rPET to 64.0 MPa and 2000 MPa, respectively, in the 10-wt% compatibilized blend. This aligns with Maris et al. [7], who highlight that compatibilizers, while beneficial for morphology, can disrupt crystalline structures and lower overall stiffness. Our DMA results similarly showed decreased storage modulus and increased creep compliance with higher compatibilizer content, underscoring this classic trade-off between toughness and stiffness in recycled polymer blends.

Despite partial improvements, our compatibilization strategy has not entirely overcome the mechanical limitations posed by mixing recycled PET with polyolefins like PP. Persistent phase separation, as evident from our DSC and morphological analyses, suggests that Lotader AX8840 alone may be insufficient for achieving a fully homogeneous blend. Additionally, the presence of contaminants such as bottle labels and caps introduces further complexity, often leading to brittleness in processed samples even when compatibilizers are used. Our results thus reflect the broader conclusion in the literature: chemical compatibilization can mitigate immiscibility but may fall short in delivering mechanical properties suitable for high-performance applications, particularly when dealing with highly heterogeneous waste streams [7–9].

To address these challenges, future research should explore combined strategies that integrate chemical compatibilization with physical morphology control. One promising avenue is microfibrillar reinforcement, as demonstrated by Friedrich et al. [9], where cold drawing transforms PET domains into fine microfibrils that enhance mechanical interlocking and stress transfer within the blend. Additionally, optimizing the concentration of compatibilizers as Imamura et al. [8] found—could balance improvements in ductility without excessively compromising stiffness, particularly if lower loading levels (~3 phr) are sufficient. Emerging approaches using nanoparticle-based compatibilizers, as noted by Maris et al. [7], also warrant investigation for their ability to migrate to polymer interfaces and stabilize morphologies. Finally, incorporating advanced sorting technologies or selective pre-treatment steps could reduce contamination levels, enabling more effective compatibilization and yielding higher-performance recycled materials. These multi-pronged strategies will be critical for enabling stand-alone recycling facilities to produce structurally viable products from mixed plastic waste streams.

3.5 Life Cycle Assessment

Beyond mechanical performance, the sustainability of recycling processes was evaluated through preliminary life cycle assessments (LCA) [6]. For stretch wrap waste, the analysis showed significant environmental benefits, with estimated savings of approximately 52,300 MJ of embodied energy and avoidance of about 558 metric tons of CO₂ emissions. These figures correspond to a 44% reduction in

embodied energy and a 13% reduction in CO₂ emissions compared to virgin material production, as illustrated in Figures 11 and 12.

Recycling PET bottles demonstrated even greater potential impact. The LCA results indicated energy savings of approximately 146,000 MJ and a reduction of about 4,900 metric tons of CO₂ emissions, translating to a 53% decrease in embodied energy and a 39% reduction in CO₂ emissions relative to virgin PET production. These improvements are also shown in Figures 11 and 12.

These analyses were based on the following assumptions regarding material composition in the waste streams: stretch wrap consisted of a 50:5:25:20 ratio of LLDPE stretch wrap, polypropylene (PP) packaging tape, LDPE stretch wrap, and HDPE packaging films, respectively. PET bottle waste was modelled as a 90:9:1 ratio of PET bottles, PP caps, and PE labels.

Overall, these findings highlight the substantial environmental benefits achievable through localized recycling operations, including reduced greenhouse gas emissions, lower energy consumption, and decreased reliance on landfill disposal or incineration in burn pits. Stand-alone recycling facilities thus offer not only technical feasibility but also meaningful contributions to resource conservation and sustainability goals [5-6].

Figure 11. CO₂ emission reduction for stretch wrap and PET from bottles.

Figure 12. Embodied energy reduction for stretch wrap and PET from bottles.

3.6 Mechanical Test Results

The mechanical properties of recycled plastics are critical indicators of their suitability for producing durable, value-added products. To evaluate the structural potential of various recycled polymer systems, flexural tests were conducted on both pure materials and compatibilized blends, providing insights into the balance between strength, stiffness, and ductility achievable through recycling processes. These results are shown in Table 2.

Sample Type	Flexural Strength (MPa)	Flexural Modulus (MPa)	Elongation at Break (%)
HDPE	23.1 ± 0.5	630 ± 20	9.2 ± 0.3
LDPE	15.3 ± 0.4	420 ± 15	8.7 ± 0.4
Stretch Wrap	15.0 ± 0.6	420 ± 10	5.3 ± 0.3
rPET	76.8 ± 1.1	2810 ± 40	2.5 ± 0.2
rPET + 5% Lotader AX8840	66.1 ± 1.0	2460 ± 35	3.6 ± 0.2
rPET + 10% Lotader AX8840	64.0 ± 1.2	2000 ± 30	4.3 ± 0.3

Table 2. Mechanical properties of recycled polymer blends.

4 FINANCIAL FEASIBILITY OF CONTAINERIZED RECYCLING FACILITIES

Assessing the economic viability of standalone, containerized materials recovery facilities (MRFs) is crucial for understanding their practical implementation, particularly in rural and remote communities. Financial analyses suggest that such systems require a minimum processing volume of approximately 400–600 tons of recyclables per year to break even, covering both capital and operational costs through

a combination of revenue from recycled material sales and savings from avoided landfill tipping fees.

The economic feasibility of these decentralized systems is highly sensitive to commodity market prices and regional tipping fees. Higher recovered material prices (\geq \$100/ton) and elevated landfill tipping fees (\geq \$50–\$70/ton) significantly enhance the potential for a positive financial return. However, many rural communities face challenges due to lower commodity prices and reduced tipping fees, which can undermine the financial sustainability of small-scale recycling operations.

Regional collaboration emerges as a key strategy to improve economic outcomes. Small towns individually often generate insufficient recyclable material volumes to sustain operations. For instance, a low-volume town with a population of approximately 5,000 may produce only around 200 tons/year of recyclables. Under a scenario of \$100/ton in revenue and avoided tipping fees, this would generate roughly \$20,000 in annual benefits, insufficient to offset estimated autonomous operating and capital costs of about \$40,000/year, resulting in a net loss of \$20,000 annually. Conversely, a regional model consolidating materials from several communities (population \sim 20,000) could yield around 800 tons/year of recyclables, translating to \$80,000/year in revenue and avoided costs. In this scenario, the same estimated operational and capital expenses would yield a positive net balance of \$40,000/year, demonstrating clear economies of scale.

Despite advances in automation and lower labor requirements, upfront capital costs for standalone containerized systems remain significant, typically around \$250,000 per unit. Consequently, grants, low-interest loans, or other financial incentives are often essential for rural communities with constrained municipal budgets to establish such facilities. Overall, while standalone containerized MRFs show promise for sustainable waste management, their deployment is most viable in regions where collaborative collection networks can be established, commodity markets are stable, and external funding support is available to bridge the gap between capital investment and operational profitability. This analysis is shown in Table 3.

Parameter	Low-Volume Town	Regional Model
Population	5,000	20,000
Tons/year recyclables processed	200	800
Annual revenue + avoided tipping fees (\$100/ton)	\$20,000	\$80,000
Autonomous O&M + capital cost per year	~\$40,000	~\$40,000
Net annual balance	–\$20,000	+\$40,000

Table 3. Financial Analysis of Standalone Containerized Recycling Facility Scenarios.

*Autonomous O&M” refers to estimated annual operation and maintenance costs for largely automated recycling systems, excluding significant manual labor costs.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This study demonstrates the feasibility of producing value-added products from post-consumer plastic waste using stand-alone, containerized recycling systems. Stretch wrap waste, composed primarily of mixed polyolefins, was successfully processed into molded products such as sheets and bricks, albeit with lower mechanical properties compared to engineering polymers. Recycled PET (rPET) displayed significantly higher stiffness and strength; however, blending rPET with polyolefins presented challenges due to inherent immiscibility. The use of Lotader AX8840 compatibilizer improved ductility and elongation at break in rPET blends but resulted in reduced flexural strength and modulus, highlighting the classic trade-off between toughness and stiffness in recycled polymer systems.

Thermal analyses via DSC confirmed the presence of multiple melting transitions in stretch wrap materials, indicating their heterogeneous composition, and revealed retained crystallinity in recycled PET suitable for processing applications. Dynamic mechanical analysis further demonstrated the impact of compatibilizer content on creep compliance, underscoring its role in modifying viscoelastic behavior and mechanical performance.

Life cycle assessment indicated substantial environmental benefits for decentralized recycling operations. Recycling stretch wrap waste could save approximately 52,300 MJ of embodied energy and reduce CO₂ emissions by 558 metric tons, while PET bottle recycling offers even greater savings of about 146,000 MJ and a reduction of 4,900 metric tons of CO₂ emissions, compared to virgin material production. These results support the environmental sustainability of localized recycling solutions.

Financial analyses revealed that while standalone containerized recycling facilities are technically feasible, their economic viability depends heavily on processing volume, market conditions, and regional collaboration. Smaller communities may not generate sufficient material to sustain operations independently, emphasizing the importance of pooling resources and securing financial support through grants or subsidies to offset capital and operational costs.

Overall, this work highlights both the technical potential and the challenges associated with decentralized recycling of mixed plastic waste streams. Future research should explore advanced compatibilization strategies, process optimization, and scalable economic models to enhance the viability of localized recycling systems and contribute to circular economy goals.

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